

On three problems concerning the Smarandache LCM sequence

Felice Russo

Via A. Infante 7

67051 Avezano (Aq) Italy

felice.russo@katamail.com

Abstract

In this paper three problems posed in [1] and concerning the Smarandache LCM sequence have been analysed.

Introduction

In [1] the Smarandache LCM sequence is defined as the least common multiple (LCM) of $(1, 2, 3, \dots, n)$:

1, 2, 6, 12, 60, 60, 420, 840, 2520, 2520, 27720, 27720, 360360, 360360, 360360, 720720

In the same paper the following three problems are reported:

1. *If $a(n)$ is the n -th term of the Smarandache LCM sequence, how many terms in the new sequence obtained taking $a(n)+1$ are prime numbers?*

2. *Evaluate $\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \sum_n \frac{a(n)}{n!}$ where $a(n)$ is the n -th term of the Smarandache LCM sequence*

3. *Evaluate $\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \sum_n \frac{1}{a(n)}$ where $a(n)$ is the n -th term of the Smarandache LCM sequence*

In this paper we analyse those three questions.

Results

Problem 1.

Thanks to a computer programs written with Ubasic software package the first 50 terms of sequence $a(n)+1$, where $a(n)$ is the n -th term of Smarandache LCM sequence, have been checked. Only 10 primes have been found excluding the repeating terms.

In the following the sequence of values of $n \leq 50$ such that $a(n)+1$ is prime is reported:

$$2, 3, 4, 5, 7, 9, 19, 25, 32, 47$$

According to those experimental data the percentage of primes is:

$$\frac{10}{24} \approx 41.7\%$$

We considered 24 instead of 50 because we have excluded all the repeating terms in the sequence $a(n)$ as already mentioned before. Based on that result the following conjecture can be formulated:

Conjecture: *The number of primes generated by terms of Smarandache LCM sequence plus 1 is infinite.*

Problem 2.

By using a Ubasic program we have found:

$$\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \sum_n \frac{a(n)}{n!} \approx \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{1}{32 \cdot n^2 + 20 \cdot n - 11} = 4.195953\dots$$

Problem 3.

Always thanks to a Ubasic program the convergence value has been evaluated:

$$\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \sum_n \frac{1}{a(n)} \approx \ln \frac{27773}{27281} = 1.7873\dots$$

where 27773 and 27281 are both prime numbers.

References.

- [1] A. Murthy, *Some new Smarandache sequences, functions and partitions*, Smarandache Notions Journal, Vol. 11 N. 1-2-3 Spring 2000.